

Using CRISPR/Cas9 to investigate the developmental roles of Fcho, Pgm3, and Nckap1 in Ciona, Part 2: testing their roles in notochord intercalation and convergent extension

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Introduction

We are currently investigating three genes of interest in the non-vertebrate chordate *Ciona robusta*: *Fcho* (*FCH* and *mu* domain-containing endocytic adaptor), *Pgm3* (Phosphoacetylglucosamine mutase 3) and *Nckap1* (NCK-associated protein 1) and their roles in the development of the notochord, the defining feature of the chordate phylum. These genes were identified as notochord-expressed orthologs of human disease-associated genes by Arcadia Science [1]. Described here is our initial work exploring the role of these genes in *Ciona* notochord convergent extension, an essential process that occurs early during notochord development. This process involves the mediolateral polarization and migration of 40 post-mitotic cells that form two rows of 20 cells on either side of the midline in the developing embryo [2]. These two rows of cells then intercalate to form a single row of cells (Figure 1). Eventually, through additional steps of elongation, vacuolization, and tubulogenesis, the notochord transforms into an extracellular fluid-filled tube that serves as a hydrostatic skeleton for the swimming *Ciona* larvae [3]. Following the initial design and validation of single-chain guide RNAs (sgRNAs) for CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis of these three genes [4], here we describe their disruption in the notochord lineage and our initial observations on potential defects in intercalation of notochord cells as a result.

Intercalation

Figure 1: schematic of intercalation process during early notochord morphogenesis in Ciona during the initial tailbud stage (Hotta Stage 17-18).

We previously measured the mutagenesis efficacies of a few sgRNAs per gene by target amplicon sequencing [4]. To knock out *Pgm3*, we used the combination of sgRNAs 1.83 and 2.27. For *Fcho*, we used the 1.34 and 5.112 sgRNA combination, and for *Nckap1*, we combined sgRNAs 2.74 and 8.103. These were previously identified as having the highest efficacies in creating insertion/deletion in our desired target regions [4]. These data are summarized in Table 1 below.

sgRNA	Mutation efficacy (indel rate)
Pgm3.1.83	23%
Pgm3.2.27	>12.5%
Fcho.1.34	43%
Fcho.5.112	>15%
Nckap1.2.74	>15%
Nckap1.8.103	>15%

Table 1: Our sgRNA combinations used in CRISPR/Cas9 experiments and their estimated efficacies based on indel frequencies in sequenced target amplicons [4]. An exact efficacy rate was not ascertained when amplicons spanned natural SNPs or indels (e.g. Pgm3.2.27, Fcho.5.112, Nckap1.2.74, and Nckap1.8.103). Instead, an efficacy “floor” was given, as efficacy was at least higher than the largest CRISPR-induced indel peak measured.

Method: intercalation defects assay

To assess the potential role of these genes in notochord cell intercalation, we performed CRISPR/Cas9-mediated mutagenesis in the *Ciona* notochord cell lineage. We used the dechoriation and electroporation protocol previously described by Christiaen et al [5, 6]. Synchronized zygotes were electroporated with gene-specific combinations of plasmids encoding the sgRNAs described in **Table 1**, together with the *Foxa.a>Cas9::Geminin^{N-terminus}* plasmid to induce mutations early in the notochord cell lineage as previously described [7]. We allowed the embryos to develop to the mid tailbud I stage (Hotta Stage 21, roughly 9.5 hours post-fertilization when reared at 20°C) when intercalation is complete in normally developed embryos. The fluorescent reporter plasmids *Brachyury>CD4::GFP* (encoding cell membrane-bound GFP), *Brachyury>Unc-76::GFP* (encoding GFP tagged with a portion of the Unc-76 protein from *C. elegans*, which promotes its cytoplasmic localization), and/or *Brachyury>H2B::mCherry* (encoding histone-fused mCherry) were also used to visualize the notochord cell shape and nuclei, respectively. A control experiment was performed using the same plasmids, using a *U6>control* sgRNA plasmid targeting no *Ciona* sequence instead of the sgRNA plasmid combination for each gene. Per 700 µl of electroporation volume, we used 80 µg of sgRNA plasmid (40 µg of each when combined), 35 µg of Cas9 plasmid, and 40 µg of each green or red reporter plasmid.

Embryos in control and knockout conditions were imaged using an inverted epifluorescence microscope and scored as either normal intercalation, minor defect in intercalation (1-2 cells out of midline) and severe defect in intercalation (3+ cells out of midline). Examples of normal and severe defects in three different conditions are shown in **Figure 1**. This semi-quantitative phenotype scoring was done following the “French Method” and its associated scoring sheet, an example of which is shown in **Figure 2**. Experiments were performed in three separate biological replicates using different batches of dissected gametes, with 75 individuals scored per condition and replicate. Raw images and scoring data for *Pgm3* and *Fcho* CRISPR embryos (but not *Nckap1* CRISPR) can be found here: <https://zenodo.org/records/17857562>

Results

Three replicates of the *Pgm3* knockout were performed, and the scoring data are summarized in **Figure 3**. In the first replicate, we observed severe notochord intercalation defects in 51% of embryos in the *Pgm3* knockout condition, compared to 23% of negative control embryos. This initially suggested that *Pgm3* could play a role in proper notochord intercalation. We performed an additional two replicates of this experiment. However, in these additional experiments, we observed roughly equal percentage of defects in both control and knockout conditions (~50% and ~30% defects in replicates two and three respectively). Since we could not replicate our initial results showing an increase in intercalation defects in *Pgm3* knockout condition compared to the control, we cannot conclude that *Pgm3* is vital for proper intercalation of notochord cells.

Figure 2: Representative epifluorescence microscopy images of early tailbud embryos showing examples scored as “normal” intercalation (top) or those with severe intercalation defects (bottom). Control = negative control CRISPR condition. Dashed outlines indicate embryo outline. Anterior always to the left or top/bottom-left. Dorsal always over ventral. All scale bars = 50 μ m. See text for details about type and amount of plasmids electroporated.

c.	Assay	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	55	60	65	70	75	80	85	90	95	100	sum	
CONTROL	Mch	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	25
	Minor 1-2 cells	-	-	-	-					/	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17
	Severe 2+	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	17

22% severe
41% total defects

Figure 2: An example of the “French Method” for scoring intercalation defects. A record of each individual transfected (*mCherry*+) embryo is kept, indicating minor or severe defects. No defects = relatively normal intercalation. Percentages are later calculated based on total *mCherry*+ embryos (top row)

Similarly, for *Fcho* CRISPR we performed the same intercalation assay over two replicates to determine if this gene was playing a role in this process of notochord morphogenesis. Scoring results are summarized in **Figure 4**, showing a slight increase in defects in the knockout in replicate one, though barely any increase in replicate two. Therefore we cannot conclude that *Fcho* is required for proper intercalation either. Finally, in a single replicate for *Nckap1* CRISPR as well, and in the first replicate, we also saw similar percentage of defects in the control vs knockout conditions, and these data are summarized in **Figure 5**.

Figure 3: Scoring of intercalation defects in *mCherry*⁺ tailbuds in control and *Pgm3* knockout conditions in three separate replicates. Replicate 3 used *Unc-76::GFP* instead of *CD4::GFP*. *n* = 75 for each condition and replicate. Control = negative control CRISPR condition.

Figure 4: Scoring of intercalation defects in *mCherry*⁺ tailbuds in control and *Fcho* knockout conditions over two replicates. *n* = 75 for each condition and replicate. Control = negative control CRISPR condition.

Figure 5: Scoring of intercalation defects in *mCherry*⁺ tailbuds in control and *Nckap1* knockout condition in one replicate. *n* = 75 for either condition. Control = negative control CRISPR condition.

Conclusions and future plans

Overall, these results do not suggest that these genes play a significant role during the early stage of intercalation in the notochord. However, we cannot rule out a role either. As can be seen from the variation in the incidence of severe defects among replicates, even in negative control embryos, it is clear that intercalation is a sensitive process that is especially susceptible to non-specific effects. These effects can arise from the myriad steps involved in generating tissue-specific CRISPR knockouts in F0 embryos, namely the chemical and enzymatic removal of the chorion (egg shell), or the transfection with plasmid DNAs by whole zygote electroporation. Intercalation may also be sensitive to environmental and/or seasonal conditions, as gametes are obtained from adult specimens collected weekly from various locations in the wild. Of note, these experiments were performed as the winter approached, and anecdotally we have noticed a drop in gamete quality during colder weather with animals collected around the Los Angeles and Orange County (California) areas. Animals collected further south (San Diego area) might retain better gamete quality deeper into the fall and winter, however the *Ciona* supplier in that area recently retired, forcing us to switch to a more northerly source. We will need to repeat these experiments when intercalation defects in the negative control approach a sustainably low frequency again, which may be only when the weather warms up again in the spring. This does bring up a recurring issue that many non-model organisms face: the influence of seasonality and/or diversity of genetic and local environmental factors on the development of wild-caught specimens. Nonetheless, even with a higher baseline incidence of intercalation defects in some control samples, we would expect an increase in defects in the parallel CRISPR samples, if these genes were heavily involved in this process.

We still hypothesize that these genes might be playing a larger role in later stages of notochord development, namely vacuolization and tubulogenesis. *Pgm3* (Phosphoglycomutase 3) is vital for proper glycosylation, and previous work has shown that glycosylation is required for proper notochord lumen expansion in *Ciona* [8]. *Fcho* is an endocytic adaptor protein important for forming clathrin pits, another process that been shown to be important in notochord lumen formation [9]. *Nckap1* is a key member in the wave regulatory complex (WRC) that regulates actin polymerization [10]. Actin has been shown to be crucial in the dynamic cell shape changes and remodeling of the notochord during tubulogenesis [11]. Thus the literature suggests that these genes could be vital these later steps of notochord development. Therefore, to continue this work, we plan to investigate the role of these genes in vacuolization, lumen expansion, and

tubulogenesis in the notochord. To do this, we will perform the same tissue-specific CRISPR/Cas9 knockouts of these genes described here, but observe embryos at the late tailbud III stage (Hotta Stage 25, roughly 15 hpf at 20°C) when extracellular lumen pockets begin to form in between notochord cells [12]. In the next phase of this project, we will assess proper tubulogenesis and the role of *Pgm3* by observing cell and lumen pocket boundaries in the developing notochord. Anecdotally, the vacuolization and tubulogenesis of the notochord appears to be less susceptible to non-specific defects than notochord intercalation, which may aid us in conclusively identifying a robust phenotype.

References

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